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Psychological Characteristics Of Personality Traits In The Mastery Of Mathematics By Students Of The “Temurbeklar Maktabi”

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Abstract: Today, achieving high results in education directly depends not only on the level of knowledge of students, but also on their personal and psychological characteristics, attitude to the educational process and the level of individual development. Especially in modern specialized educational institutions - in particular, in educational institutions operating in a military-patriotic spirit, such as the "Temurbeklar Maktabi", the process of mastering mathematics requires students to have a high level of intellectual activity, responsibility, logical thinking and psychological stability. This work analyzes the role of psychological characteristics of personality qualities in the mastering of mathematics by students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi", how they affect their academic activity and how such characteristics can be developed.

Key words: Personality traits, cognitive (cognitive) characteristics, motivation, self-regulation, socio-emotional characteristics, high discipline, leadership skills, analytical thinking, strategic decision-making.

Introduction.

Temurbeklar School is a specialized educational institution in the Republic of Uzbekistan that educates young people in the spirit of patriotism, leadership, discipline and responsibility. The name of the school was chosen based on the legacy of the great commander Amir Temur, and the motto is based on the principle of “Strength is in justice”.

1. Main goals:

- formation of leadership qualities,
- development of military and civil leadership skills,
- upbringing of physical, mental and spiritual perfection,
- strengthening national pride and patriotism.

2. The concept of leadership skills

Leadership skills are the ability to lead a team, make decisions, share responsibility and inspire others.

3. Mechanisms for the formation of leadership skills

The following methodological approaches are used in Temurbek schools: Military-disciplinary training: training in formation preparation, command execution, mutual respect between leader and subordinate. Leadership training and role-playing games: team management, conflict resolution, decision-making exercises.

4. Project activities: teach students to take independent initiative and responsibility. Studying the personality and legacy of Amir Temur: studying leadership qualities through a historical figure. Motivational and patriotic activities: form internal motivation that leads students to the goal.

At the Temurbeklar School, these skills are formed in the following areas:

Direction	Skill to be developed
Military-disciplinary training	Organizational discipline, order, responsibility
Physical training	Willpower, endurance
Spiritual and educational education	Moral leadership, justice, and honesty
Psychological preparation	Emotional stability, decision-making in a problematic situation
Teamwork	Leadership, communication skills, sharing of responsibilities

Scientific and methodological foundations Amir Temur - as a model of leadership. His work "Temur's Regulations" outlines the main qualities of a leader - justice, order, determination, patriotism. These principles are at the heart of the educational work of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi". From the point of view of modern educational psychology, leadership requires a high level of socio-emotional intelligence.

Daniel Goleman's theory of "Emotional Intelligence" explains this aspect. The pedagogical approach in student-centered education is that leadership skills are formed through "learning by doing".

In the modern educational process, the level of students' mastery of knowledge is closely related to their individual psychological characteristics. Each student demonstrates his own educational activity according to his temperament type, willpower stability, emotional state and motivation system. From this perspective, it is an important scientific issue to study the psychological characteristics of students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" in mastering mathematics, to identify their personality traits and to analyze the impact of these traits on the learning process.[3]

Mathematics is the main type of intellectual activity that forms the logical, analytical and creative aspects of human thinking, and in the process of mastering it, the student's attention, memory, logical thinking, patience and willpower are actively manifested. Especially for students studying at the "Temurbeklar Maktabi", mathematics not only develops mental potential, but also strengthens the psychological components of military-disciplinary training - determination, responsibility, quick thinking and the ability to make decisions in a problematic situation.

From the perspective of personal psychology, motivation (the internal driving force of learning), volitional qualities (goal-seeking, patience, determination), cognitive processes (attention, thinking, memory), and emotional stability play an important role in the successful mastery of mathematics.

In this regard, determining the attitude, learning motives, and personal qualities of the students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" to mathematics allows for the psychologically effective organization of their learning activities.[4]

In addition, an individual approach in mathematics education, taking into account the personal differences of students, creating a positive motivational environment and managing the affective (emotional) state, significantly improves learning outcomes. These issues are even more relevant in the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" educational system, creating the need to develop psychological analyses and practical recommendations in this direction.

Scientific foundations of the hypothesis.

1. Theoretical foundations of personality psychology.

Personality psychology is a branch of psychology that studies the individual characteristics of a person, the laws of the formation of his mental states, motivation, temperament, character and volitional qualities. The success of a person in his educational activities depends mainly on his cognitive processes (perception, thinking, memory, attention), emotional and emotional stability and motivational orientation.

There are a number of theoretical approaches to studying personality in psychology:

The behaviorist approach (J. Watson, B. Skinner) explains individual behavior through incentives and punishments in the external environment. According to this approach, the student's interest in mathematics is also strengthened by positive assessment, recognition and encouragement given by the teacher.[5,6]

The cognitive approach (J. Piaget, L. Vygotsky, J. Bruner) justifies the growth of a person's ability to think, perceive, analyze and generalize in the process of mastering knowledge. In the process of teaching mathematics, it is precisely cognitive development, that is, the level of logical thinking of the student, that occupies a central place.[2,4]

Humanistic psychology (A. Maslow, K. Rogers) interprets a person as a being striving for self-awareness, realization of his potential and self-development. According to this approach, mathematics develops in the student a sense of self-assertion, independent thinking, and personal achievement.[7,8]

The socio-psychological approach (A. Bandura, L. Vygotsky) emphasizes that students' success in the educational process is formed through the social environment, interaction with the teacher, collective learning, and social examples.

Thus, the psychological development of a person in mastering mathematics is a complex process, which occurs as a result of the interaction of cognitive (knowledge), affective (emotional), and volitional components.[9,10]

1.2. Cognitive processes of a person in mastering mathematics.

Mathematics, by its very nature, requires a high level of abstract thinking, logical analysis, and finding solutions to problem situations. Therefore, students' cognitive processes - perception, attention, memory, thinking, and speech - are the main psychological foundation in mastering this subject.

Perception is the ability to correctly perceive mathematical symbols, shapes, numbers, and formulas. If a student perceives a problem incorrectly, he will make a mistake throughout the entire solution process.

Attention is the main mental process in the process of solving mathematical problems, which requires stability and stability. Attention control in students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" may be relatively developed due to military-disciplinary training.

Memory plays an important role in the process of memorizing and restoring formulas, theorems, algorithms, and proofs.

Thinking is a mental activity aimed at identifying logical connections, generalizing, analyzing, and solving a problem.

Speech is inextricably linked with thinking as a means of expressing mathematical thought.[2,4]

The harmonious development of these processes creates the basis for students' conscious mastery of mathematics.

1.3. Psychological mechanisms of motivation and educational activity.

Motivation plays a central role in mastering mathematics. Students' internal need to learn, interest in science, and striving for goals directly affect the effectiveness of education.

In psychology, educational motives are divided into two types:

Internal motives - a natural interest in learning, a desire to learn new things, a desire for self-development.

External motives - grades, awards, recognition from teachers or parents, a system of incentives.

For students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi", external motives - discipline, competition, a sense of responsibility - can be a strong source of motivation. At the same time, for successful mastery of the subject, it is important to form internal motivation, arouse interest in the subject, and give a sense of success.[2,4,11]

1.4. The role of volitional and emotional factors.

Volitional qualities — patience, determination, independence, and self-control — are of particular importance in mastering mathematics. A student may repeatedly fail to solve a logical problem, in which case volitional stability encourages him to solve the problem.

The emotional state, on the other hand, controls the attention of students and affects the thinking process. A positive emotional background (confidence, interest,

motivation) activates educational activity, while negative emotions (fear, anxiety, distrust) inhibit mental activity. Therefore, the teacher and psychologist need to create a positive psychological atmosphere in the learning environment.[2,4,12]

1.5. Individual differences in learning performance.

Individual differences in learning mathematics depend on temperament, character, learning style, and learning experience. For example:

Sanguine students are active but easily distracted;

Phlegmatic students are stable but slow;

Choleric students are strong-willed but emotional;

Melancholic students may be cautious but insecure.

Therefore, adapting teaching methods to the psychotype of the individual, that is, using a differential approach, increases educational effectiveness.[2,4,13]

1.6. The relationship between mathematics and discipline.

Mathematics is a subject that requires logic, determination, attention and patience. Therefore, it directly affects the formation of high discipline in students.

Requires logical thinking. To solve mathematical problems, the student is forced to think step by step, systematically. This develops the discipline of thinking.

Teaches patience and persistence. The need to re-solve the problem several times forms the habit of patience and self-improvement in the student.

Teaches systematicity and adherence to a clear plan. In studying mathematics, topics are presented sequentially - this develops the student's ability to plan his activities and manage time.

It forms fearlessness and analysis. In mathematics, mistakes are a natural part of learning. Analyzing errors increases self-regulation skills.[14]

Conclusion.

Students of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" are individuals who require comprehensive development not only intellectually, but also socially and psychologically. In mastering mathematics, their personal and psychological qualities - motivation, willpower, emotional balance, temperament and the level of development of cognitive processes - are of great importance.

Research shows that students' mathematical thinking and academic success are inextricably linked with their individual and psychological characteristics. In particular, such volitional qualities as internal motivation, self-control and patience play a decisive role in achieving high results. In the conditions of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" external factors - discipline, competition, teamwork and patriotism - shape students' positive attitude towards learning, but for the sustainable effectiveness of education, internal interest and striving for self-development are necessary. In the process of mastering mathematics, along with the development of cognitive processes such as attention, thinking, perception, and memory, managing the emotional state of

students, creating a positive psychological environment, and using an approach that is appropriate to individual differences increase the effectiveness of education. In general, the study of the psychological characteristics of students of the “Temurbeklar Maktabi” in mastering mathematics serves as an important scientific and practical basis for individualizing the educational process, developing a person-oriented pedagogical approach, and increasing the psychological competence of the teacher.

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